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Towards Understanding the Nexus Between Religion, Conflict and Peacebuilding in Africa

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Abstract

This research argued that the place of religion in conflict and peacebuilding in Africa, cannot be over-emphasized. Africans are notoriously religious, and religion permeates every aspect of their existence. However, African continent in many respects has experienced political, economic, cultural and religious retardation due to wars and crises that have bedevilled her over the years. No society thrives in a chaotic, violent and conflict situation. Hence, there is no option to peace and peaceful co-existence if any meaningful development is to be achieved by any society. This work adopted phenomenological and sociological methods in examining the key issues raised; while data were collected using secondary sources. The paper discovered that while religion could cause conflict, religion is intrinsically good and plays important role in the restoration of peace and tranquillity in Africa, through dialogue, oath taking, advocacy and preaching and teaching. It is rather man's perception, uncanny behaviour, approach and use of religion that made it look as if it plays ambivalent roles. No world religions have claimed to be a violent religion. Religious leaders, government agencies were advised to engage proper religious tenets in addressing conflict situations in Africa in order to drive peace and development in the continent.

Keywords: Religion, Conflict, Peacebuilding, Development, Africa

Introduction

Religion is a body of truths, beliefs, laws, rites and attitudes by which man subordinates and relates to the transcendent being. It plays important roles in the society, such as, the promotion of peace and tranquillity, social cohesion, shaping of human ethics and source of moral and spiritual development. It is an integrative force and engenders social stability (Obaje, 2018). These functions of religion have been exemplified in Africa, as religion is said to be to some extent the second nature of the African people. Religion cuts across all sphere of African existence ranging from birth to death. It defines the peoples' outlook and permeates all aspects of life. Thus Mbiti (1969) affirmed that, "Africans are notoriously religious."

Conflict is seen as the incompatibility of interests, goals, values, needs, expectations and/or social cosmologies, which can lead to clash, competition or interference of opposing forces (Dennen, 2005). Conflict in all forms and manner, is a threat to human peaceful co-existence and development. No people or nation progresses in the face of conflict. Africa, for many decades has been overtaken by series of conflicts ranging from war, insecurity, religious turmoil, intercommunity disputes, to say the least (Kanu & Ndubuisi, 2020). The results of these crises include, loss of human lives, destruction of properties and the general dislocation of the ecosystem. Unfortunately, most of these conflicts have religious undertone. Thus, how can religion therefore, foster peace in the face of being seen as an instrument of violence?

Peace, a state of quiet or tranquillity, absence of war or conflict, freedom from disturbance or agitation, has become the desire of everyone (Obaje, 2018). Peace is a condition for development in any society. Where peace exists, people live without fear, there is progress in all endeavours. All world known religions preach peace and discourage conflict in any form. The dominant religions in Africa: Christianity, Islam and African Traditional Religion preach peace as well.

Religion has great influence in peacebuilding process in Africa. Using various methods and means, religion has encouraged the principle of nonviolence in its efforts to entrench peace in Africa (Tanko, Lemon & Kajan, 2014). The importance of being proactive, mediation, education, inculcating the religious virtues and tenets and dialogue, have been

explored at various times to promote peace in Africa by religious groups (Tanko, Lemon & Kajan, 2014).

The main objective of this research, is to examine the positive functions of religion in conflict situations and how religion has helped in promoting peace in Africa. Sociological and descriptive methods were adopted, while data were gathered using secondary sources. The essence of avoiding conflict and enthroning peace was highlighted if Africa will experience meaningful development. The roles of religion in achieving this cannot be trivialized. In the next sub-heading, the researcher will explicate few concepts that form the major thrust of this work.

Delineating the Key Concepts

Understanding the key concepts of religion, conflict and peace, is of great essence in this work, as this throws more light into the subject matter under consideration. The term *religion* has become many things to many people, as many have grown weary when the word ‘religion’ is mentioned (Nwankwo, 2018). The use of the word ‘religion’ is gradually joining an “alarmist club” of sensitive terms. There are over one thousand and one definitions of religion as there are many religions in the world (Obilor, 2010). Religion is seen differently by different people. To a scientist, a philosopher, a theologian, an anthropologist and ethnographers, religion is viewed and defined in perspective. Hence, no single definition will suffice when it comes to understanding the concept comprehensively (Obilor, 2010).

According to Silvestri and Mayall (2015), religion is most commonly understood to be a system of beliefs and values associated with particular organizational forms (e.g. ritual practices, institutions), and with a supra-natural deity embodying and emanating some absolute truths. While Obilor (2010) sees religion as, “the whole *complexus* of attitudes, beliefs, practices, gestures, rituals, emotions, convictions, and institutions through which we express our deep fundamental relationship with Reality and not excluding the created order.” Religion is a strong ideology and conviction which may seem difficult to resist once conceived. It encompasses the totality of human person and explains the deep fundamental questions bordering on reality, essence and existence (Nwankwo, 2018).

On conflict, Ramsbotham, Woodhouse and Miall (2005) noted that “it is an expression of the heterogeneity of interests, values and beliefs that arise as new formations generated by social change come up against inherited

constraints.” Tanko, Lemon and Kajan (2014) said that, “conflict is seen as the existence of non-compatibility or disagreements between two actors (individuals, groups, organizations or nations) in their interaction over the issues of interests, values, beliefs, emotions, goals, space, positions, scarce resources.” Conflict occurs when two or more persons engage in a struggle over values and claims in order to secure status, power and resources; a struggle in which the objectives of the opponents are to neutralize, injure or eliminate their rivals. It is an opposition between two simultaneous but incompatible wishes or impulses, sometimes leading to emotional tension. It could also mean to come into opposition, clash or to fight (Tanko, Lemon & Kajan, 2014).

Peace is generally concerned with the creation and maintenance of an ordered and just society. It is an absence of war, which orchestrates justice, development, respect and tolerance between people (Francis, 2006). Peace is a process involving activities that are directly or indirectly linked to increasing development and reducing conflict. It relates to existing social conditions, rather than an ideal state or condition. Accordingly, Obaje (2018), affirmed that peace is a state of quiet or tranquillity, freedom from disturbance or agitation. It is a dynamic process which is capable of identifying precisely the factors that drive it. It is not a finished condition, but always a ‘work-in-progress.’ Peace increases or decreases depending on objective, socio-economic and political conditions (Tanko, Lemon & Kajan, 2014).

Theoretical Framework

Theoretical framework, is the structure that can hold or support a theory of a research study. It introduces and describes the theory which explains why the research problems under study exist (William, 2006). Thus, for this research, conflict theory of Karl Marx and Johan Galtung Mini theory of peace, shall form the basis for this study.

The conflict theory as propounded by the German philosopher Karl Marx (1818-1883), is a social theory that discusses the ensuing conflict between the rich and the poor in the society to control scarce resources. Karl Marx stated that conflict will persist in society due to the limited resources and people’s struggle to control and dominate. Conflict is viewed as a process of competition, struggle, and dominance. Conflict theory understands society as being made up of individuals competing for scarce resource which is at

the heart of all social relationships. Karl Marx view on religion came as a result of the prevailing circumstances of the society and the struggle between the various classes (Obaje, 2018). In this theory, Karl Marx postulates that religion functions as the opium of the people. It is used as a tool of oppression and at the same time a source of relief and control to the oppressed who are prone to violence.

On the other hand, Johan Galtung (1964) Mini Theory of Peace, posits that peace is a relation, between two or more parties. The parties may be inside a person, a state or nation, a region, religion or civilization, pulling in different directions. Peace is not a property of one party alone, but a property of the relation between parties. Galtung (1964), identified three forms of relations that exists: negative disharmonious (what is bad for one is good for the others); ii. indifferent (a non-relation, they do not care about the other); iii. positive harmonious (what is bad-good for one is bad-good for other). In reality, relations may be mixes of all three. When the negative relation is brought about with intent, the party is an actor, then the result is direct violence, harm or war, depending on the degree. If the violence to a party is not intended, it can be described as indirect, often caused by inequitable structures producing harm; and then the role of culture legitimizing either or both types of violence, (cultural violence). Furthermore, Galtung (1964), distinguished between 'positive peace' (the absence of indirect violence) and 'negative peace' (the absence of direct peace).

Both theories of Karl Marx and Johan Galtung, are much relevant to this work. One of the enablers of conflict is oppression occasioned by manipulation of the lower class by the upper class in the society. To suppress aggression and violence, religion, therefore, becomes a tool. Again, peace exists as a relation between various parties. Whichever this relation turns, determines whether peace will follow or conflict.

Religion and the African Society

Africa is the home of many religions, because *religion informs everything in traditional African society*, including politics, art, marriage, health, diet, dress, economics, and death (Olupona, 2015). This corresponds with Mbiti's assertion, that Africans are notoriously religious (Mbiti, 1969). The three dominant religions in Africa are: Christianity, Islam and African Traditional Religion (ATR). Christianity, has around 49% of Africans as its

adherents, with so many denominations all over the continent. Islam has about 42% of Africans affiliated to it; while African Traditional Religion, has only 8% of Africans patronizing the religion today (Uzundu, 2020). Christianity and Islam are classified as “introduced religions” whereas traditional African religions are vast and varied “lived religions,” passed down over generations of oral tradition.

Understanding African religiosity cuts across all spheres of religious influence on the people’s outlook. It is far beyond a matter of adherence to a doctrine or ideology, but is concerned with supporting fecundity and sustaining the community as provided by the major religions in the continent (McKenna, 2025). To Africans, religion emphasizes maintaining a harmonious relationship with the divine powers, and their rituals attempt to harness spiritual powers and channel them for good. Ritual is the means by which a person negotiates responsible relationships with other members of the community. It is done with a view to maintaining peaceful coexistence of the both the living, the dead and the created order.

Religion and Conflict in Africa

The fact that religion influences Africans, cannot be disputed. This has been repeated severally in this work and confirmed by other scholars (Oluduro 2010; Athyo 2013). Through religion, African continent has experienced development in various aspects. It has alluded elsewhere, that religion plays ambivalent roles. It is a force that unites and sues for peace and development and at the same time a force that has led to numerous conflicts in Africa. It is evident in the sense that Africa has for decades been devastated by numerous conflicts, including religious crises. This is true of many African countries like Nigeria (Warner 2012).

The rise in religious discrimination in Africa has coincided with a rise in religious armed conflicts. The quest to expand from one area to the other has led ethno-religious conflicts witnessed in Africa today (Basedau, 2017). There are various reasons why religion breeds conflict in Africa. The content of religion and its tenets can be a factor in conflict, especially, as it concerns the roles of religion to the society. Jihadist rebellions as seen in Mali or Nigeria are good examples of conflict occasioned by varying theological contents.

Again, conflict involving Christians and Muslims, can thus be likened to an interfaith conflict. Interfaith or interreligious conflicts include cases in

which big sub-denominations like Protestants and Catholic Christians or Sunni and Shia Muslims clash. Interreligious conflicts can also be, but are not necessarily over religious ideologies or content (Basedau & Schaefer-Kehnert, 2018).

Religious discrimination generally may lead to conflict, especially those with religious overtones. Some of the conflicts that occur in the Middle Belt of Nigeria and along the culturally borderline states of the predominantly Muslim North, and between Hausa-Fulani groups and non-Muslim ethnic groups in the South, happen as a result of discrimination (Osaghae and Subeni 2005).

Another factor leading to religious conflict is the clashing interests of those in authority (Eche & Okechukwu, 2020). A Nigerian example will suffice here. It was observed that the ruling class has applied a number of processes to express their dissatisfaction with exclusion from important decision-making processes in the country. The methods employed include religious violence. It has been reported that majority of the religious conflicts in Northern Nigeria, are due to the large number of rich Southerners who live and do business there. Northern elites are usually hurt by the business prowess of the Southerners and to express their grievances, they employ religious calls to incite people to destroy properties belonging to non-natives. The results are conflicts and crises fought under the pretence of being religious (Falola 1998). The effects have been very disastrous to both parties and the entire nation. This is the case wherever religious conflicts are witnessed in Africa.

Impacts of Conflicts on Development

Discussing the general impacts of conflicts, Utin (2018) noted that, when conflicts erupt, the effects are usually, catastrophic. Conflicts alienate people from their relatives, families, and friends. The most painful effect of conflict is the tendency to loss of human lives and resources.

Dorsouma (2024) agreed that conflicts impact development and sustainability significantly in the negative, leading to economic reduction, social dislocation, humanitarian disasters, and environmental degradation. These include impacts of natural resources such as wildlife, protected areas, vital ecological locations and other natural ecosystems.

At least about 20 percent of global conflicts occur in Africa (Dorsouma, 2024). This is a big threat to the national economies, societies and human

environment. At the moment, the impacts of conflicts on Africa are the reasons for resources drain and diversion, leading to decline in economic growth, decrease in agricultural production, and cause of food insecurity and rising costs living generally. Furthermore, conflicts lead to migration which increases pressure on natural resources, competition between communities, exacerbate poverty, governance issues, and ecological disasters (Dorsouma, 2024).

Oyinlola, Adeniyi, and Adedeji (2020) affirmed that conflicts are undoubtedly destructive for a country in all ramifications. Due to nonexistence of enabling environment, countries affected by conflicts may find it difficult to sustain economic growth and development. This is the case in Africa, where persistence of conflicts has been one of the major indices that contributed to under-development in the region (Ezeoha, 2015). Consequently, the resulting effect of crises has embodied disasters and other events where the survival of the society is at stake. This can also cause destruction that can lead to widespread human, economic, material or environmental dislocations, that is beyond what available resources can handle (Dunne & Mhone, 2003).

Religion and Peacebuilding in Africa

Tanko, Lemon & Kajan (2014) affirmed that peacebuilding describes the interventions designed to prevent the occurrence or resumption of conflict within a nation by creating avenues for sustainable peace. It is an activity aimed at addressing the root causes or potential causes of violence, create a societal expectation for peaceful conflict resolution and stabilize society politically and socio economically (Huxley, 1979). Peacebuilding involves all stakeholders and institutions like the state, religious bodies, tribes, families and the likes to creating a conducive atmosphere necessary for individuals to live harmoniously without war, strife, conflict and rancour (Uzonde, 2020).

Methods through which Religion Can Foster Peace in Africa

Interreligious Dialogue

Inter and intra-faith dialogue, respectively, refers to cooperation, discussion, constructive, and positive communication between and among members of the same and different religious traditions (Steen-Johnsen, 2020). It illustrates how spiritual and/or religious principles may be used to

advance peace at both personal and social level (Christoph, 2018). The promotion of peace is the aim of the religious participants in conflict management discussions.

African continent is majorly affected by religious conflicts. A peace process based solely on secular values will probably not be sustainable. This is because in times of conflict, religious believers from different faiths often find that they have more in common with one another than they have with non-religious people (Abokwe, 2020).

Studies have shown that interfaith dialogue is essential in polarized society, and that religion can be a source of peace instead of war and violence in Africa. On this, Abu-Nimer, Khoury and Welty, (2007), noted that, interfaith dialogue contributes toward conflict resolution because its concept of reconciliation, involves processes of confession, repentance, mercy, and forgiveness. These processes are drawing on religious resources as the basis for dialogue. Africans are deeply religious, so bringing religion into the dialogue allows the participants to engage in the process, with their religious identity as their primary point of reference (Abu-Nimer, Khoury & Welty, 2007).

Religious Advocacy

Advocacy is one of the main functions of religious players in peacebuilding (Paffenholz, 2003; Christoph, 2018). Communication channels offered by religious leaders, could raise the public's consciousness and make it simpler for topics to be added to the public agenda, targeting the interests of the excluded. In other words, religious actors work to increase the involvement of government, particularly its inclusiveness. (Gopin, 2000, 2002, Ossai 2021, Johnsen, 2020). In order to build peace, it is therefore crucial to articulate specific interests of the parties involved, bring pertinent issues to the public's attention, establish communication channels, raise public awareness and engage the public in discussion, and participate in formal peace procedures (Deng, 2022). This way peace could be restored in conflict infested regions.

Oath Taking

Oath taking in African tradition is conceptualized as a solemn promise made by an individual or group of persons, with a deity as a witness. Mbiti, (2022), maintained that oaths are administered on individuals or community to

promote and strengthen bonds of friendship and foster good human relationship. It binds the people mystically, thus, restraining them from hostility against themselves.

Ajakor and Ojukwu (2019) noted that, oath taking is one of the methods used in traditional African society to prevent, manage and resolve conflict. This was a practice to establish truth and guilt and discourage dishonest attitude and evil actions in society (Oguntomisin 2004). Most times, this was done at the shrine of a very powerful deity over something that could be an avenue for contacting such deity. It is a ritual that involves blood covenant (Nwolise, 2005; Ademowo, n.d). People are always warned before taking oath on the consequence of doing so on falsehood in order to avoid shame, or even death.

Studies in different parts of Africa, reveal that oaths help to discourage violence, conflict, dishonest attitudes and evil actions by members of different communities, thereby promoting peace and conflict resolution (Ajayi & Buhari, 2014).

Religious Education

Uzundu (2020) made a detailed discussion on how peacebuilding could be achieved through religious education. Religious education inculcates morality responsible for character formation of the youths. This has the capacity to restraining them from violence in a crisis situation. Moral formation is obtained through religious education and moral agents like parents, teachers, and pastors/priests. Christian education, Christian ethics or moral philosophy, mould children's and youths' character through religious-ethical principles. The tenets of religions are very key for all, as religious education helps people develop an understanding of themselves and others. Religious education promotes the spiritual, moral, social and cultural development of individuals, groups and communities. This in a way could lead to tolerance, peace, understanding, forgiveness, love and solidarity. All these are necessary for peacebuilding. (British Broadcasting Corporation, 2018).

Conclusion

This paper underscored the important roles played by religion in Africa towards resolving conflicts and ensuring that social harmony and peace exist in the society. Africa, as a nation, has experienced various degrees of

conflicts with some having religious undertones. Conflict undermines growth and development; while peace is the only condition for meaningful achievement in any nation. The three dominant religions in Africa preach peace. Though the adherents of these religions do go out of their ways in using religion to create problem in the society. Yet religion, through various methods has weighed in to restore peace in conflict devastated societies. Thus, emphasizing the indispensability of religion in fostering peace.

Recommendations

The work, therefore, recommends that:

1. The religious leaders should engage the various methods enunciated in this work to entrench peace. Such as dialogue, religious education, advocacy and oath taking.
2. The adherents of the major religions in Africa should imbibe the tenets of love, forgiveness and tolerance, as these values will promote peace and development.
3. The religious leaders should avoid divisive messages in their preaching and teaching and rather emphasize on those that promote peace in the society.
4. Political leaders should desist from using religion to divide the people and incite violence, in other to achieve their selfish interests.

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